

PHYSICS AND MATHEMATICS

EXPLORATION OF METHODS FOR PROVING INEQUALITIES BASED ON CALCULUS THEORY

Yang Xiuchuan

School of Mathematics and statistics, JiNing Normal University,
Ulanqab, Inner Mongolia, P. R. China

Abstract

The proof of inequalities is a core subject in mathematical analysis, with methods that are both diverse and skillful. Calculus, taking functions as the object of study, provides systematic and profound methodological support for proving inequalities through core concepts such as limits, derivatives, integrals, and series expansions. This paper systematically explores typical strategies for proving inequalities using calculus tools such as function monotonicity, Mean Value Theorem, Taylor's Formula, function extrema and maximum(or minimum), and convex function theory. Combined with classic examples, it analyzes their application skills and ideological connotations, revealing the powerful tool nature and inherent logical unity of calculus in proving inequalities.

Keywords: Calculus; Inequalities; Mean Value Theorem; Taylor Expansion; Convex Functions.

1. Introduction

Inequalities, as fundamental objects of mathematical research, are widely permeated in many fields such as algebra, geometry, and analysis. Methods for proving inequalities in elementary mathematics (such as the comparison method, synthetic method, and reduction to absurdity) mostly rely on specific skillful transformations and have limited universality. The emergence of calculus has broken this limitation: it takes functions as the core research object, depicts the instantaneous rate of change of functions through derivatives, and describes the cumulative effect of functions through integrals, providing a new ideological method for proving inequalities from the perspective of "dynamic change". The core logic of using calculus to prove inequalities is: convert the inequality problem into a function problem, establish the magnitude relationship between function values by studying the properties of functions such as differential mean value characteristics, Taylor expansions, extrema and maximum(or minimum), and convexity, and then derive the target inequality.

2. Exploration of Typical Methods and Their Applications

2.1 Proving Inequalities Using Function Monotonicity

(1) Theoretical Basis

Function monotonicity is a basic property of functions. Its core criterion is: if a function $f(x)$ is differentiable on an interval I , and for any $x \in I$, $f'(x) \geq 0$ (or $f'(x) \leq 0$), then $f(x)$ is monotonically increasing (or decreasing) on I . Based on this, inequalities can be proved by constructing an auxiliary function and using derivatives to judge its monotonicity.

(2) Methodology

After transposing the expressions on both sides of the inequality to make one side zero, the other side can be constructed as the auxiliary function $f(x)$, converting the original inequality into the form $f(x) \geq 0$ (or $f(x) \leq 0$); calculate $f'(x)$, judge its sign on the target interval, and determine the

monotonicity of $f(x)$; combined with the function value at the endpoint of the interval (usually zero), derive the sign of $f(x)$ within the interval using monotonicity, thereby completing the proof.

(3) Application Example

Prove: When $x > 0$, $\ln(1+x) < x$.

Proof: Construct the auxiliary function $f(x) = x - \ln(1+x)$, which needs to prove that $f(x) > 0$ when $x > 0$. Taking the derivative, we

get $f'(x) = \frac{x}{1+x}$. When $x > 0$, $f'(x) > 0$,

thus $f(x)$ is monotonically increasing on $(0, +\infty)$

. Moreover, $f(0) = 0$, therefore when $x > 0$

, $f(x) > 0$, that is, $\ln(1+x) < x$.

(4) Key Points for Exploration

The core lies in constructing an appropriate auxiliary function whose derivative is easy to analyze and whose endpoint value can directly reflect the inequality relationship. When constructing, it is necessary to flexibly transpose, transform, or introduce intermediate functions according to the form of the target inequality.

2.2 Proving Inequalities Using Mean Value Theorem

(1) Theoretical Basis

Lagrange's Mean Value Theorem is a core tool, whose content is: if a function $f(x)$ is continuous on $[a, b]$ and differentiable in (a, b) , then there exists $\xi \in (a, b)$ such

that $f(b) - f(a) = f'(\xi)(b - a)$.

(2) Methodology

Express the increment $f(b) - f(a)$ of the function on the interval as the product of the derivative $f'(\xi)$ at a certain point and the interval length $(b - a)$, and establish an inequality about $f(b) - f(a)$ by estimating the range

of $f'(\xi)$ (such as maximum value, minimum value, upper and lower bounds).

(3) Application Example

Prove: When $b > a > 0$

$$\frac{b-a}{b} < \ln \frac{b}{a} < \frac{b-a}{a}.$$

Proof: Let $f(x) = \ln x$, then $f(x)$ is continuous and differentiable on $[a, b]$, and $f'(x) = \frac{1}{x}$. Applying Lagrange's Mean Value Theorem to $f(x)$ on $[a, b]$, there exists $\xi \in (a, b)$ such that $\ln b - \ln a = \frac{1}{\xi}(b-a)$, that

$$\text{is, } \ln \frac{b}{a} = \frac{1}{\xi}(b-a). \text{ Since } a < \xi < b, \text{ we}$$

have $\frac{1}{b} < \frac{1}{\xi} < \frac{1}{a}$, and since $b > a > 0$, therefore

$$\frac{b-a}{b} < \frac{b-a}{\xi} < \frac{b-a}{a}, \text{ that is,}$$

$$\frac{b-a}{b} < \ln \frac{b}{a} < \frac{b-a}{a}.$$

(4) Key Points for Exploration

This method is particularly suitable for inequalities involving function differences. The key is to effectively estimate the range of the derivative $f'(\xi)$ within the interval $(b-a)$ (using the boundedness, monotonicity, etc., of the derivative). Cauchy's Mean Value Theorem can be further used to handle inequalities in the form of ratios.

2.3 Proving Inequalities Using Taylor's Formula

(1) Theoretical Basis

Taylor's Formula is an important tool for local approximation of functions. Its content is: if a function $f(x)$ has $n+1$ -th order derivatives in an open interval I containing the point x_0 , then for any $x \in I$,

$$f(x) = f(x_0) + f'(x_0)(x-x_0) + \frac{f''(x_0)}{2}(x-x_0)^2 + \dots + \frac{f^{(n)}(x_0)}{n!}(x-x_0)^n + R_n(x)$$

where the Lagrange form of the remainder $R_n(x)$ is

$$R_n(x) = \frac{f^{(n+1)}(\xi)}{(n+1)!}(x-x_0)^{n+1} \text{ (with } \xi \text{ between } x_0 \text{ and } x).$$

(2) Methodology

Expand the function at a specific point (often an extreme point, interval endpoint, or special point) into the sum of a Taylor polynomial and a remainder. Derive the inequality by analyzing the signs and magni-

tudes of each term in the expansion, as well as the estimation of the remainder, combined with known conditions.

(3) Application Example

$$\text{Prove: } e^x \geq 1 + x + \frac{1}{2}x^2 (x \geq 0).$$

Proof: Expand $f(x) = e^x$ at $x_0 = 0$ into the second-order Taylor formula (with Lagrange remainder): $e^x = 1 + x + \frac{x^2}{2!} + \frac{e^\xi}{3!}x^3$, where ξ is between 0 and x . Because when $x \geq 0$, $x^3 \geq 0$ and $e^\xi > 0$, the remainder $\frac{e^\xi}{6}x^3 \geq 0$. Therefore,

$$e^x \geq 1 + x + \frac{1}{2}x^2 (x \geq 0).$$

(4) Key Points for Exploration

This method is suitable for inequalities that require high-precision approximation or involve high-order derivatives. Choosing an appropriate expansion point x_0 and expansion order n is crucial, and the estimation of the remainder directly affects the derivation of the inequality.

2.4 Proving Inequalities Using Function Extrema and maximum(or minimum)

(1) Theoretical Basis

If the establishment of an inequality is related to the maximum or minimum value of a function on a certain interval, the inequality can be proved by finding the extrema or maximum(or minimum) of the function. Specifically: if the minimum value of a function $f(x)$ on an interval I is m , then for any $x \in I$, $f(x) \geq m$; if the maximum value is M , then $f(x) \leq M$.

(2) Methodology

Construct an auxiliary function $f(x)$, converting the original inequality into the form $f(x) \geq 0$ (or $f(x) \leq 0$); find $f'(x)$, set $f'(x) = 0$ to solve for critical points, and judge whether the critical points are extreme points by combining the change of the derivative sign; calculate the function values at the extreme points and interval endpoints to determine the maximum(or minimum) of the function on the interval; if the minimum value is greater than or equal to 0 (or the maximum value is less than or equal to 0), the inequality holds.

(3) Application Example

$$\text{Prove: For any real number } x, e^x \geq 1 + x.$$

Proof: Construct the auxiliary function $f(x) = e^x - x - 1$, which needs to prove that $f(x) \geq 0$ for any $x \in R$. Taking the derivative, we get $f'(x) = e^x - 1$. Setting $f'(x) = 0$, we solve for the unique critical point $x = 0$. When $x < 0$, $f'(x) < 0$, and $f(x)$ is monotonically decreasing;

when $x > 0$, $f'(x) > 0$, and $f(x)$ is monotonically increasing. Thus, $x = 0$ is the extremal point (also the minimum point) of $f(x)$, and $f(0) = e^0 - 0 - 1 = 0$. Therefore, for any real number x , $f(x) \geq 0$, that is, $e^x \geq 1 + x$.

(4) Key Points for Exploration

The logic for constructing the auxiliary function is similar to that of the monotonicity method. The core is to determine the maximum (or minimum) of the function through derivative analysis and use the relationship between the maximum (or minimum) and 0 to prove the inequality.

2.5 Proving Inequalities Using Convex Function Theory

(1) Theoretical Basis

The core properties of convex functions include: if a function $f(x)$ is a convex function on an interval I , then for any $x_1, x_2, \dots, x_n \in I$ and positive

weights $\lambda_1, \lambda_2, \dots, \lambda_n$ (satisfying $\sum_{i=1}^n \lambda_i = 1$),

Jensen's Inequality

holds: $f(\sum_{i=1}^n \lambda_i x_i) \leq \sum_{i=1}^n \lambda_i f(x_i)$. In addition, a

convex function can be judged by the second derivative: if $f''(x) \geq 0$ holds for any $x \in I$,

then $f(x)$ is a convex function.

(2) Methodology

Identify or prove that the function involved in the target inequality is a convex (or concave) function, and directly apply Jensen's Inequality or other properties of convex functions (such as the tangent line being below the function, the secant line being above the function) to derive the inequality.

(3) Application Example

Prove the Arithmetic-Geometric Mean Inequality: For positive numbers x_1, x_2, \dots, x_n ,

$$\frac{1}{n}(x_1 + x_2 + \dots + x_n) \geq \sqrt[n]{x_1 x_2 \dots x_n}.$$

Proof: Consider the function $f(x) = -\ln x$ (with domain $x > 0$). Calculating the second derivative: $f''(x) = \frac{1}{x^2} > 0$,

so $f(x)$ is a convex function on $(0, +\infty)$. Applying

Jensen's Inequality, take $\lambda_i = \frac{1}{n}$ (for $i = 1, 2, \dots, n$),

then:

$$f\left[\frac{1}{n}(x_1 + x_2 + \dots + x_n)\right] \leq \frac{1}{n}[f(x_1) + f(x_2) + \dots + f(x_n)]$$

.Substituting $f(x) = -\ln x$, we get:

$$\begin{aligned} -\ln\left[\frac{1}{n}(x_1 + x_2 + \dots + x_n)\right] &\leq -\frac{1}{n}(\ln x_1 + \ln x_2 + \dots + \ln x_n) \\ &= -\ln \sqrt[n]{x_1 x_2 \dots x_n} \end{aligned}$$

Multiply both sides by -1 (reversing the inequality direction):

$$\ln\left[\frac{1}{n}(x_1 + x_2 + \dots + x_n)\right] \geq \ln \sqrt[n]{x_1 x_2 \dots x_n},$$

Since $\ln x$ is monotonically increasing,

$$\frac{1}{n}(x_1 + x_2 + \dots + x_n) \geq \sqrt[n]{x_1 x_2 \dots x_n}.$$

(4) Key Points for Exploration

Convex function theory provides a highly unified perspective for proving inequalities. Many classic inequalities (such as Hölder's Inequality and Minkowski's Inequality) are essentially manifestations of convexity. The key is to construct an appropriate convex (or concave) function according to the form of the inequality and flexibly apply its properties.

3. Conclusion

The theoretical ideas of calculus, especially the ideas of depicting function changes through derivatives and describing cumulative effects through integrals, have opened up a systematic, profound, and highly powerful path for proving inequalities. The function monotonicity method reflects the direct depiction of the increasing or decreasing trend of functions by derivatives; Mean Value Theorem reveals the inherent connection between the overall change of a function and the local rate of change within an interval; Taylor's Formula provides a precise tool for approximating global behavior using local high-order information of functions; the extremum and maximum (or minimum) method establishes universally valid magnitude relationships through the "extreme states" of functions; convex function theory provides a highly unified aesthetic framework for proving inequalities from both geometric and analytical perspectives. These methods do not exist in isolation but are interrelated and complementary, collectively forming a rich toolbox for proving inequalities using calculus. A deep understanding and flexible application of these methods and the essence of their underlying ideas can not only effectively solve various inequality problems but also deepen the understanding of function properties, limit ideas, and the inherent unity of calculus, thereby improving mathematical analysis ability.

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